

International Conference 2025:
Towards Resilient and Sustainable Cities and Communities

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17041983

Enhancing Basic Education as a Foundation for Resilience and Sustainability in Low-Income Mega-Cities: the Case of Lagos, Nigeria

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Abstract: The provision of quality basic education is critical for building resilient and prosperous communities. This is particularly needed in low-income settings, where enhancing education can develop human capital and the development of sustainable infrastructures for energy, the built environment, sanitation and more. Nigeria as home to the world's largest population of out-of-school children and the mega-city of Lagos State can shed light on the challenge of education provision in comparable cities across the globe.

This research takes a whole system perspective on basic education provision in Lagos State, focussing on policy and other stakeholder influences on the education system. The research draws on grounded thematic analysis of 18 semi-structured interviews with education stakeholders, including teachers, government officials, parents and NGO representatives.

The findings reveal a range of structural barriers to quality basic education provision, such as inadequate infrastructure, overcrowded classrooms, limited access to technology and weak safeguarding mechanisms. Despite strong efforts to enhance provision through systematic use of education technology in Lagos State and policies for improved teachers' skills development, many gaps in implementation persist.

The research leads to over 10 practical recommendations to strengthen policy and practice in Lagos State, including more integrated continuous professional development for teachers, improved resource allocation and multi-stakeholder collaboration in the education system. The Lagos State case study offers insights that will have value across cities and implications for locations facing similar challenges to basic education provision across the globe.

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Keywords: “Basic Education”, “Education Policy”, “Lagos State”, “Educational Infrastructure”, “Teacher Professional Development”

Main highlights:

- Quality basic education builds resilient and inclusive urban communities.
- Lagos State schools face overcrowding, weak infrastructure and resource gaps.
- Teachers’ professional development lacks follow-up, mentorship and practical relevance.
- EdTech impact is limited by infrastructure and skills gaps.
- Children with disabilities remain largely excluded from mainstream education.
- Policy to practice gaps and weak stakeholder collaboration hinder education reform.
- Systemic improvements need holistic, multi-stakeholder and sustained action.

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Introduction

The provision of quality basic education is widely recognised as a cornerstone for building resilient, inclusive and prosperous communities (UNESCO, 2015). Beyond its intrinsic value, education serves as a powerful enabler for broader societal outcomes, including economic productivity, improved health, civic participation and environmental stewardship (ibid). In low-income urban contexts, where infrastructure deficits, socio-economic inequalities and rapid population growth interconnect, the role of education becomes even more heightened (Auwalu and Bello, 2023). Strengthening basic education in such settings has the potential to enhance human capital while simultaneously fostering the conditions necessary for sustainable development, such as informed citizens, innovation and the adoption of resilient urban systems (Marco, 2017).

Nigeria presents a particularly urgent case for examining the state of basic education provision. As the most populous country in Africa, it is home to the world's largest population of out-of-school children, with estimates exceeding 10 million (Nwoke, Oyiga and Cochrane, 2024). In addition, in many regions across the globe, substantial barriers limit access to this important service, leading to Nigeria accounting for one in every five out-of-school children worldwide (UNICEF, 2025). This challenge is compounded by rapid urbanisation, especially in Lagos State, the country's economic nerve centre and one of the largest mega-cities globally (Akinyemi *et al.*, 2014). Lagos's population, estimated at over 16-21 million, continues to grow at a pace that strains existing infrastructure, including schools (Idris and Fagbenro, 2019). The city's complex socio-economic system, marked by significant inequalities, creates an environment where access to quality education is highly uneven, often reflecting broader patterns of deprivation.

The Lagos State education system operates within this challenging context. While the government has made commendable strides in expanding access, introducing education technology (EdTech) initiatives such as the EKO EXCEL programme and improving teacher training (Akinyemi *et al.*, 2014), persistent gaps remain in implementation and impact. Overcrowded classrooms, low confidence among teachers, lax admission processes, weak (Adeniran, Ishaku and Akanni, 2020) and safeguarding mechanisms and insufficient infrastructure undermine the delivery of quality basic education. Furthermore, policy ambitions often weaken in practice due to funding constraints, governance challenges and the limited integration of stakeholder perspectives into decision-making processes.

This paper adopts a whole system perspective on basic education provision in Lagos State, recognising that the performance of the education sector is shaped not only by practices in schools but also by the interplay of policy frameworks, governance structures, socio-economic conditions and community engagement. By focusing on the relationships between these elements, this paper seeks to provide a more holistic understanding of the factors enabling or constraining educational quality in low-income mega-city contexts.

The study draws on 18 semi-structured interviews with diverse education stakeholders, including teachers, government officials, parents and representatives of non-governmental organisations (NGOs). These perspectives provide rich qualitative insights into both the

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systemic challenges and the opportunities for reform. The findings reveal structural barriers such as inadequate infrastructure, overcrowding, limited access to technology and weak safeguarding mechanisms, as well as areas of promise in teacher professional development, EdTech deployment and collaborative governance.

Therefore, this paper is guided by the following question:

What strategies and interventions can strengthen basic education provision in low-income mega-city settings, drawing on lessons from the Lagos State case study?

By addressing this questions, this paper aims not only to contribute to academic debates on education in low-income urban contexts but also to provide actionable recommendations for policymakers, practitioners and community stakeholders seeking to improve educational outcomes and, by extension, urban resilience and sustainability.

Literature Review

The role of education in fostering urban resilience extends beyond its direct impact on literacy and numeracy outcomes. As articulated in resilience theory (Folke, 2006), education equips communities with the skills, knowledge, and adaptive capacities needed to respond to environmental, economic, and social shocks. In mega-cities such as Lagos, where vulnerability to climate risks, health crises, and socio-economic instability is heightened, a robust education system contributes to societal adaptability. This is not only through human capital development but also via civic engagement, innovation in problem-solving, and the embedding of sustainable practices within the cultural fabric of the community.

Basic education underpins the development of resilient, inclusive and sustainable communities (UNESCO, 2015). In alignment with Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 4, access to quality education is a human right and an enabling condition for achieving other global targets, including health equity, gender equality and climate resilience (UNICEF, 2021). Research consistently shows that investment in basic education correlates with increased economic productivity, stronger governance and improved environmental stewardship (World Health Organisation, 2020). In low-income contexts, education also plays a central role in breaking cycles of poverty and fostering civic engagement.

Research from other low-income mega-cities such as Dhaka, Bangladesh, and Kinshasa, Democratic Republic of Congo, reveals strikingly similar patterns of educational constraint such as overcrowded classrooms, limited teacher training and insufficient infrastructure, often exacerbated by rapid, unplanned urbanisation (Titeca and de Herdt, 2011; Ahmed *et al.*, 2019). These parallels suggest that the systemic challenges in Lagos are not isolated but form part of a broader global phenomenon in which governance and resource constraints intersect with demographic pressures to undermine the realisation of universal basic education. By studying Lagos, insights can be generated for other urban centres experiencing similar constraints, allowing for the adaptation of policy interventions to local contexts while drawing on shared lessons.

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With a population exceeding 20 million and rapid annual growth, Lagos State faces one of the most pressing urban education challenges globally (Adedeji, 2024). While the Lagos State Ministry of Education has implemented reforms such as Education Technology (EdTech) integration through the EKO EXCEL programme and teacher development programmes, many initiatives face implementation bottlenecks due to governance gaps, infrastructure constraints and limited stakeholder engagement (Ybnu *et al.*, 2024). Moreover, Mishra and Koehler's (2019) Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK) framework emphasises that effective digital-age teaching requires the seamless integration of technology, pedagogy and content knowledge.

This paper applies a whole systems perspective (Meadows, 2008) to examine the interdependent policy, institutional and community factors influencing education. It also draws on social capital theory (Putnam, 2000), which highlights the role of trust, collaboration and networks in improving service delivery.

Methodology

This study adopts a pragmatic paradigm (James, 2019), prioritising practical solutions over strict adherence to a single epistemological stance. This paradigm supports the integration of multiple perspectives from diverse education stakeholders to address the research question and achieve the study objectives. A mixed methods design was employed, combining quantitative and qualitative approaches to provide a more holistic understanding of the systemic influences on basic education provision in Lagos State. As (Creswell, 1999) notes, this combination enables the integration of numerical patterns with rich, narrative insights, yielding findings that neither approach could achieve independently. This methodological flexibility also makes it possible to address complex, context-dependent issues with both breadth and depth.

The qualitative analysis utilised grounded thematic analysis (Braun and Clarke, 2006) to explore stakeholders' lived experiences and perceptions. A purposive sample of 18 education stakeholders was recruited, comprising 11 public primary school teachers, 2 government officials, 3 parents and 2 representatives of non-governmental organisations (NGOs). Semi-structured interviews lasting between 45 and 90 minutes were conducted, recorded with informed consent, and transcribed verbatim. The interview guide included open-ended questions exploring challenges, opportunities, and the impact of policy on education provision. Transcripts were analysed using Braun and Clarke's (2006) six-phase process: familiarisation, coding, theme generation, review, definition, and reporting. The quantitative strand followed a "bottom-up" approach, applying bivariate and multivariate analyses (Teachman, 1980; Pfeifer, 1999) to identify emerging trends, which were then interpreted alongside the qualitative findings.

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Results

The thematic analysis identified six overarching themes:

Infrastructure and Resource Deficits

Participants overwhelmingly described inadequate facilities as a fundamental barrier to quality education. Reports of overcrowding, unsafe structures and a lack of basic resources were common.

"In my school, we have over 70 pupils in one classroom. Sometimes, we put two classes together when a teacher is absent. It's very hard to manage that number, and some children just switch off" - Teacher

"When it rains, the roof leaks. We move pupils to the dry corners and keep going. But it distracts everyone, and the younger children get scared" – Parent

"Even basic teaching materials like chalk and textbooks are not always available. Teachers often buy them from their salaries" – Teacher

Overcrowded classrooms in Lagos often exceed UNESCO's recommended 35:1 pupil–teacher ratio, negatively impacting learning outcomes. The link between inadequate infrastructure and reduced engagement has also been documented in low-income urban contexts globally (Darling-Hammond, Hyler and Gardner, 2017).

Teacher Capacity and Professional Development

While Lagos State has introduced training programmes, participants emphasised the lack of sustained, continuous professional development (CPD).

"We attend training, but it's just a one-day thing. No one follows up to see if we are using the new methods"– Teacher.

"Mentorship is missing. If experienced teachers could guide the younger ones, the quality would improve" – Teacher

"Sometimes the training is too theoretical. We need practical strategies that work in overcrowded classrooms" – Teacher

Therefore, CPD without follow-up risks becoming a tick-box exercise. Sustained capacity-building, embedded within teachers' daily routines, is beneficial to create long-term pedagogical change (Darling-Hammond, Hyler and Gardner, 2017).

Education Technology (EdTech) Potential and Limitations

EdTech initiatives in Lagos State, through the EKO EXCEL programme have shown promise but face infrastructural and capacity barriers.

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"We got tablets for learning, but there's no light to charge them. Sometimes, we go weeks without electricity" – Parent

"Some teachers don't know how to use the devices well, so they just put them aside" – NGO Representative

"EdTech is exciting for the pupils, but when the internet fails, it disrupts the lesson completely" – Teacher

This resonates with findings by Lagos State Ministry of Education, who note that technology provision must be accompanied by infrastructure investment and digital literacy training. Without these, devices risk being underused or abandoned (Ahmed *et al.*, 2019).

Policy Implementation Gaps

Participants consistently described a disconnect between policy intentions and realities on the ground.

"We have good policies on paper, but they are not practical in the classrooms we have" – Teacher

"Monitoring is weak. A policy is launched, but no one checks if it is being done properly" – Government Official

"Sometimes policies change with new administrations, so there's no continuity" – NGO Representative

These issues mirror the governance challenges identified in (Akinyemi *et al.*, 2014), where weak monitoring and political discontinuity undermine educational reforms.

Equity and Inclusion in Education Access

Children with disabilities remain underserved, lacking the resources and trained staff needed for inclusion.

"My child has hearing difficulties, but there is no special assistance in the school" – Parent.

"Disabled children are sometimes told to stay at home because teachers don't know how to teach them" – NGO Representative

"Inclusive education here is still a dream. Even the buildings are not accessible" – Teacher

These findings echo UNESCO's (2017) position that inclusive education in low-income contexts requires both infrastructural and pedagogical reforms.

The six themes illustrate a systemic interplay between physical infrastructure, human capacity, policy governance and equity. The findings confirm that in low-income mega-cities like Lagos State, addressing one element (e.g., EdTech provision) without parallel investment in others (e.g., electricity, teacher training) leads to limited or unsustainable improvements.

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Discussion

The results of this paper highlight a deeply interconnected set of systemic challenges in the provision of basic education in Lagos State. Each theme is not isolated; rather, they overlap to create a reinforcing cycle of inequity, limited capacity and governance gaps. These results are consistent with the whole systems perspective (Meadows, 2008), which emphasises that outcomes emerge from the dynamic interaction of multiple subsystems, for example infrastructure, teacher capacity, technology, policy, stakeholder collaboration and inclusion.

Infrastructure as a Foundation for Learning

The widespread reports of overcrowded classrooms, unsafe structures and lack of basic teaching materials reflect a structural deficit that undermines any pedagogical reform. Similar patterns have been documented in other low-income mega-cities, such as Dhaka (Ahmed, 2019) and Nairobi (Darling-Hammond, Hyler and Gardner, 2017), where infrastructure constraints are a major determinant of learning outcomes. UNESCO (2017) emphasises that safe, well-equipped schools are a prerequisite for quality education. Within a whole systems framework, inadequate infrastructure is not merely a resource problem, it also shapes teacher motivation, student attendance and the feasibility of implementing new teaching methods. For instance, interactive pedagogies requiring group work are impractical in severely overcrowded classrooms.

Stakeholder Engagement and Collaboration

A lack of coordinated action among stakeholders was widely noted.

*"If government, NGOs, and schools worked together, we could solve many problems faster"–
NGO Representative*

"Parents are rarely consulted. They just call us when they need us to attend a meeting, but decisions have already been made" – Parent

"Collaboration works when we involve everyone from the beginning, but that doesn't happen often" – NGO Representative

This reflects the literature on participatory governance, which argues that multi-stakeholder collaboration improves policy relevance and sustainability (Marco, 2017).

Teacher Capacity and the Limits of Training Opportunities

The results suggest that professional development in Lagos often lacks depth, continuity and relevance to classroom realities. Darling-Hammond et al. (2017) argue that effective CPD must be sustained over time, include active learning and be embedded in teachers' daily practice. In the absence of structured mentorship and follow-up, training risks being a one-off event with minimal impact. From a social capital perspective (Putnam, 2000), mentorship systems can build professional networks among teachers, facilitating peer learning and the exchange of

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context-specific solutions. This is especially critical in environments with high student–teacher ratios and limited resources, where adaptive expertise is beneficial.

EdTech: Potential and Pitfalls

The provision of tablets and other devices in Lagos State reflects a global trend towards digital learning solutions in resource-constrained contexts. However, as the results indicate, without stable electricity, internet connectivity and teacher digital literacy, such interventions often underperform. The application of the TPACK framework in educational practice cultivates a nuanced understanding of learning dynamics, encouraging educators to adopt a holistic, responsive approach in the digital age (Misra, 2019) as merely introducing devices does not automatically translate into improved learning outcomes; they must be integrated into coherent pedagogical strategies.

Policy to Practice Gaps

Participants' observations of weak monitoring, political discontinuity and impractical policies mirror findings in broader African education governance research (Akinyemi *et al.*, 2014). Whole systems thinking suggests that policy reforms fail when they are not co-designed with the actors responsible for implementation. Furthermore, rapid policy turnover, often linked to political cycles, disrupts continuity and erodes trust in reform efforts (World Health Organisation, 2020). To close the gap, UNESCO (2017) recommends embedding monitoring and evaluation mechanisms directly into policy design, with transparent accountability structures involving multiple stakeholders.

Collaboration and Social Capital Deficits

The limited engagement of parents, NGOs and communities in education governance reflects a breakdown in bonding and bridging social capital (Putnam, 2000). In Lagos State, siloed interventions implies that resources are duplicated in some areas and absent in others. However, systemic resilience often depends on integrated, multi-stakeholder approaches where responsibilities and resources are shared.

Inclusion as a Marker of Systemic Equity

The exclusion of children with disabilities from meaningful education access remains a significant equity gap. UNESCO's (2017) Global Education Monitoring Report emphasises that inclusive education benefits all learners, yet it requires investment in both physical accessibility and teacher training. In Lagos State, the absence of assistive devices, inaccessible buildings and untrained teachers perpetuates exclusion. This exclusion contravenes the rights of a child (UNICEF, 1989), underscoring the urgency of targeted inclusion policies.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This paper suggests that the provision of quality basic education in Lagos State is hindered by a convergence of structural deficits, capacity limitations, policy-practice gaps and weak collaboration among stakeholders. These challenges are characteristic of systemic issues found in other low-income mega-cities, highlighting the need for holistic and integrated approaches

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to reform. Importantly, the findings reveal that interventions must be multi-dimensional while addressing infrastructure and teacher capacity alongside governance and inclusion. A narrow focus on singular solutions, such as EdTech provision without addressing electricity and training, is unlikely to yield sustainable improvements. Instead, resilience in the education system depends on coordinated investment across multiple elements of change.

From a theoretical standpoint, applying a whole-systems perspective and social capital theory has illuminated the connection of the challenges and the role of trust and collaboration in enabling effective reform. This suggests that education policy in Lagos State should not only target material deficits but also focus on building the institutional relationships and community engagement necessary for sustained progress. To enhance resilience, Lagos State should also consider cross-sectoral partnerships that link education reform with health, housing and environmental planning. Such integration can amplify the impact of education by addressing the multi-dimensional elements of exclusion and underachievement. For example, school feeding programmes can improve both attendance and learning outcomes while also tackling child malnutrition.

Another critical recommendation is the establishment of a data-driven monitoring and evaluation (M&E) system that collects real-time information on infrastructure conditions, teacher performance and student attendance. This system should be publicly accessible to improve transparency and enable civil society organisations to hold policymakers accountable. The use of geographical mapping could help identify resource poor areas and prioritise resource allocation. Finally, Lagos State should engage in policy learning exchanges with other global mega-cities facing similar challenges. Such exchanges can accelerate innovation by adapting proven strategies from contexts like Nairobi's community-based teacher mentorship model or Mumbai's urban school cluster networks.

Looking ahead, the Lagos State case study offers valuable insights for comparable cities across the Global South, especially those grappling with rapid urbanisation, inequality and governance constraints. While the local context is unique, the structural patterns and reform opportunities identified here can inform a globally relevant blueprint for strengthening basic education as a foundation for resilience and sustainability in low-income mega-cities.

References

Adedeji, A. (2024) '24 PRIMARY EDUCATION IN LAGOS STATE: IDENTIFYING THE GAPS IN SERVICE DELIVERY', 8, pp. 24–37.

Adeniran, A., Ishaku, J. and Akanni, L.O. (2020) 'Is Nigeria experiencing a learning crisis: Evidence from curriculum-matched learning assessment', *International Journal of Educational Development*, 77, p. N.PAG. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijedudev.2020.102199>.

International Conference 2025: Towards Resilient and Sustainable Cities and Communities

Ahmed, A.Y. (2019) 'Data-based decision making in primary schools in Ethiopia', *Journal of Professional Capital and Community*, 4(3), pp. 232–259. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1108/JPCC-11-2018-0031>.

Ahmed, A.Y. *et al.* (2019) 'Mapping inequality in access to meaningful learning in secondary education in Ethiopia: implications for sustainable development', *Educational Studies*, 45(5), pp. 554–581. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/03055698.2018.1509777>.

Akinyemi, S. *et al.* (2014) 'Input-Output Analysis of Eko Project Training Programme in , Nigeria', *American Journal of Educational Research*, 2(5), pp. 245–249. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.12691/education-2-5-2>.

Auwalu, F.K. and Bello, M. (2023) 'Exploring the Contemporary Challenges of Urbanization and the Role of Sustainable Urban Development: A Study of Lagos City, Nigeria', *Journal of Contemporary Urban Affairs*, 7(1), pp. 175–188. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.25034/ijcua.2023.v7n1-12>.

Braun, V. and Clarke, V. (2006) 'Using thematic analysis in psychology', *Qualitative research in psychology*, 3(2), pp. 77–101.

Creswell, J.W. (1999) 'Chapter 18 - Mixed-Method Research: Introduction and Application', in G.J. Cizek (ed.) *Handbook of Educational Policy*. San Diego: Academic Press (Educational Psychology), pp. 455–472. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-012174698-8/50045-X>.

Darling-Hammond, L., Hyler, M.E. and Gardner, M. (2017) *Effective Teacher Professional Development*. Learning Policy Institute. Available at: <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=ED606743> (Accessed: 4 January 2025).

Folke, C. (2006) 'Resilience: The emergence of a perspective for social–ecological systems analyses', *Global Environmental Change*, 16(3), pp. 253–267. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2006.04.002>.

Idris, J. and Fagbenro, A. (2019) 'Lagos the Mega-City: A Report on How the Metropolis Handled an Outbreak of the Ebola Epidemic', in G.B. Tangwa *et al.* (eds) *Socio-cultural Dimensions of Emerging Infectious Diseases in Africa*. Cham: Springer International Publishing, pp. 281–298. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-17474-3_21.

James, W. (2019) 'Pragmatism - A New Name for Some Old Ways of Thinking by William James : With a Critical Introduction by Eric C. Sheffield', pp. 1–200.

Marco, R. (2017) *Education for Sustainable Development Goals: learning objectives*. UNESCO Publishing.

Meadows, D. (2008) *Thinking in Systems: International Bestseller*. Chelsea Green Publishing.

Misra, P.K. (2019) 'Equipping Teacher Educators for Digital Teaching and Learning: Promises, Practices, Challenges, and Strategies', in *Handbook of Research on Faculty Development for Digital Teaching and Learning*. IGI Global Scientific Publishing, pp. 119–139. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-5225-8476-6.ch007>.

International Conference 2025: Towards Resilient and Sustainable Cities and Communities

Nwoke, C., Oyiga, S. and Cochrane, L. (2024) 'Assessing the phenomenon of out-of-school children in Nigeria: Issues, gaps and recommendations', *Review of Education*, 12(3), p. e70011. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1002/rev3.70011>.

Pfeifer, R. (1999) 'Dynamics, morphology, and materials in the emergence of cognition', in *Annual Conference on Artificial Intelligence*. Springer, pp. 27–44.

Putnam, R.D. (2000) *Bowling Alone: The Collapse and Revival of American Community*. Simon and Schuster.

Teachman, J.D. (1980) 'Analysis of population diversity: Measures of qualitative variation', *Sociological Methods & Research*, 8(3), pp. 341–362.

Titeca, K. and de Herdt, T. (2011) 'Real governance beyond the "failed state": Negotiating education in the Democratic Republic of the Congo', *African Affairs*, 110(439), pp. 213–231. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1093/afraf/adr005>.

UNESCO (2015) *World Education Forum 2015 Final Report*. Available at: <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000243724/PDF/243724eng.pdf.multi> (Accessed: 15 March 2025).

UNESCO (2017) *Accountability in education: meeting our commitments | Global Education Monitoring Report*. Available at: <https://www.unesco.org/gem-report/en/publication/accountability-education-meeting-our-commitments> (Accessed: 15 August 2025).

UNICEF (1989) 'Convention on the Rights of the Child'.

UNICEF (2021) *The state of the global education crisis: a path to recovery: a joint UNESCO, UNICEF and WORLD BANK report*. Paris: UNESCO, cop. 2021.

UNICEF (2025) *Education | UNICEF Nigeria*. Available at: <https://www.unicef.org/nigeria/education> (Accessed: 9 March 2025).

World Health Organisation (2020) *Innovating for early childhood development: what have we learned to strengthen programming for nurturing care? Meeting report, Geneva, Switzerland, 13-14 June 2019*. World Health Organization.

Ybnu, M.T. *et al.* (2024) 'Analysis of the Implementation of Training and Development Programs for Teachers in the Context of Curriculum Change: Evaluation and Recommendations', *Dinasti International Journal of Education Management And Social Science*, 5(6), pp. 1868–1876. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.38035/dijemss.v5i6.2918>.